

Review

A Reviewal Journey of Social Entrepreneurship in The 4th Id: With A Reference of the Grameen Bank, Bangladesh

Methun Molla*

Faculty of Business and Social Entrepreneurship, University of Kuala Lumpur (Unikl), Malaysia

***Corresponding author**

Accepted: 20 July, 2020; Online: 10 August, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3978760>

Abstract: Entrepreneurship seems to have been the motor behind the rapid expansion of the social sector and also the productivity of enterprises. Furthermore, Mohammad Yunus, who founded Grameen Bank, was awarded the Noble peace prize in 2006 to promote social entrepreneurial spirit. It's a profitable business that has helped thousands of people-especially women-out of inequality. Grameen Bank is indeed the largest international microcredit organization. Social entrepreneurship has progressively found its position on the global stage as a human response to social and environmental issues, while at the same time seeking to achieve financial, social or environmental goals through entrepreneurship initiatives. The aim of this article is to examine and explore recent social entrepreneurial advancements in the present era as an essential historical event

Keywords: Business, Social Entrepreneurship, Development in Community Innovation.

INTRODUCTION

A classic illustration of a change to social enterprise in Bangladesh is Grameen Bank (GB) and its founder. Prof. Muhammad Yuns, social businessman, banker, economist and leading civil-society activist in Bangladesh, will received the Nobel Peace Prize to establish the GB and develop micro-credit and microfinance ideas. All such loans are granted to entrepreneurs that are either too impoverished for traditional bank lending. The supporters of the social enterprise idea claim that it is arbitrary and groundless to attribute the key position of social enterprise in addressing social concerns and, in particular, job development (Cook et al, 2000).

The social enterprise scheme is thought to be incapable of offering a alternative to structural poverty. Another issue is that social enterprise is incapable of measuring social impacts and social

principles. It is hard to determine if social enterprise justifies the funds invested in the financial and cultural context and if it adds to social growth. GB has stood by paying its bills interest and then recycling the assets for other females. GB introduced inspiration, creativity, immediate intervention, bravery and strength to his enterprises, demonstrated its viability and, over two centuries, created a global network of other organizations that replicated or adjusted his template to other nations and cultures and established microcredit as a worldwide sector.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the context of social problem solving, the idea of entrepreneurship that has been long hallowed in commercial organizations has been more and more utilized (Dees, 1998; Emerson & Twerksy, 1966; Thake & Zadek, 1997). There is considerable difficulty in seeking effective and sustainable solutions to several problems in society, and approaches that involve much of the ingredients associated with successful business innovation in a set of long-term poverty-related problems; these issues also involve major changes in the institutional, socioeconomic structures (Alvord et al., 2004).

Several literature work have examined the common features of effective interventions to improve the economy (e.g., Krishna, Uphoff & Esman, 1997; Tendlar, 1989). Many scholars concentrated on only the operational features as well as the structural characteristics of effective planning organizations (e.g. Brown & Covey, 1987; Korten, 1980; Paul, 1982; Gamson, 1975; McAdam, McCarthy & Zald, 1996; Tarrow, 1998; Alvord et al, 2004).

This article provides a large analysis first of all on industry, then explicitly on social enterprise and stresses the behavioral characteristics of entrepreneurship. Firstly, we broaden the scope of industry and afterwards social enterprise thus giving a brief overview to the practices of social entrepreneurs.

Ultimately, we examine the characteristics and key expectations of business performance that are supposed to be experienced by a successful entrepreneur through social enterprise research. Entrepreneurship as a portal for social enterprise. The interpretation of the phrase "social enterprise" shall be originally defined by the phrase "entrepreneurship." When business has no specific significance so societal reform does not do much.

Trade is a mutual gift. The terms trade. On and around the brighter side, there is a remarkable and inherent potential for the understanding and use of possibility, which blends out - of-the-box thinking with a rare firm commitment to producing or developing anything new or revolutionary. On either the contrary, entrepreneurship is an ex post term, because entrepreneurship takes some time until its actual effect is apparent (Martin & Osberg, 2007).

WHAT WOULD BE ENTREPRENEURSHIP?

Social entrepreneurship definitions vary from broad to small. Well into the earlier, social business applies to creative operation with a socio-profit purpose, for example in social businesses (e.g., Dees & Anderson, 2003; Emerson & Twersky, 1996) or in corporate social business (e.g., Austin, Leonard, Reficco & Wei-Skillern, 2004), in the non-profitable or across industries, such as hybrid institutional structures. In its strict definition, social enterprise is usually concerned with business expertise and market-based competency in the anti-profit sector, including creative earnings management methods by non-profit organizations (Reis 1999; Thompson 2002). (Reis 1999; Thompson 2002). The idea that the overarching impetus for social enterprise would be to promote social value rather than individual and corporate capital (e.g., Zadek & Thake 1997), and therefore that operation is defined by creativity or the development of something new rather than simply the replication of existing firms and activities, which is popular throughout all meanings of social entrepreneurial existence seems to be that. The social problem is being addressed, and the specific interpersonal structure a social enterprise takes should be predicated on the layout wherein the assets to solve the problem are most potentially mobilized. Social enterprise, as it may be performed in various vehicles, is thus not specified by the legally binding document. Nonetheless, social entrepreneurship examples can be found in the non-profit, business or government industries or can include them. In addition, social business is described as a method for reacting to market failures by means of innovation aimed at resolving social issues that are transformational and financially sustainable. The three key elements are

1. Market failure thought process
2. Innovation disruptive
3. Economic security-more information are covered following.

1. If a social entrepreneur tackles consumer defaults he can realize there will be: No demand-beneficiaries cannot compensate something, so expenses must therefore be entirely subsidised (example: Resolve to Stop the Abuse Programme: quoted in: Social Innovative, 2008). small sector-recipients are able to pay, and the social contractor can therefore rely on received revenues to support the program (Example: ITN America quoted in: Social innovator, 2008). Benefit markets-recipients are able to make the full cost payments, and so the social businessperson can generate a profit. Nonetheless, there may be an underdevelopment of the business or expenditure in this sector may produce upwards of expected results for profit-making businesses (Example: Beneath).

2. Completely new inventions or creative adaptations of solutions can possibly be transformative alternatives. Development is not really a one-off occurrence for companies, either corporate or cultural (Public Innovator, 2008). 3). Economic viability can be accomplished over a confluence of: non-financial resources-skilled or unqualified vets and one or repeated in-kind donations that enable social entrepreneurs to enhance their legislative efforts ' sufficiency. Consistent income streams involve, given the circumstances of a market distortion, long term, recurrent, and results-based financing sources-based finance, including the person, state, company, and surcharge-based financial support that will provide predictable funding. Who is a social entrepreneur? An person, community, collective, association or coalition of entities that pursue positive, vast-scale reform by break-downs of ideas about what and/or how governments, non-profits & corporations cope with important social challenges. Such list includes eight basic assumptions about the origins, objectives and approaches of social enterprise corporations, their social enterprise entities or the less ambitious entities they are developing or creating or turning into a complete-scene social enterprise.

1. There can also be small groups or teams of people, organisations, networks and even neighborhoods that join together to build pattern-breakable improvement. The premise that such a field gets to move away from local studies and increases the number of conceivably current social innovators (Bryna & Levin, 1991).

2. Fiscally feasible, significant change is sought for social entrepreneurs. Nonetheless, this presumption, which adopts the dominant goal of the present discourse, shifts the issue from

who becomes an entrepreneur to what they want and again increases the number of potential social entrepreneurs (social entrepreneurship, 2006). (Social entrepreneurship).

3. Social entrepreneurship may include innovations that disrupt trends in how or what is achieved to fix widespread social challenges.

4. In and between both industries, social entrepreneurs live. That presumption extends the conversation to other markets and multi-sector organisations in addition to non-profits. Public enterprise in policy, for example, where there are severe consequences for risk management, can be more challenging to start and maintain, but still persists. Again the idea of "sector-bending" organizations, incorporating non-profit and profit-making components, is also embraced by Dees and Anderson (social enterprise, 2006).

5. Public companies do not need to engage in social business or use market-based methods in order to succeed. This presumption removes the important yet unsatisfactory connection among social enterprise and social innovation by considering gain some of the several potential ways of achieving a valid purpose. Effective social enterprises must use the most effective systems, tactics including funding mechanisms in order to attain their economic goals," writes Dees (2004). Social enterprise should never be used as an investment technique and should not be associated with the concept of entrepreneurship. The main focus is on the creation of new and better ways of creating value "(p. 17). Importantly, Dees ' most recent work provides a way to distinguish between various forms of social disruption by the use of market-driven instruments such as this micro-finance (Bryna & Levin, 1991).

EVOLUTION AND HISTORY OF SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Social entrepreneurs have been promoted by Gen X for a prolonged time. Innovative artists of the 19th millennium are regarded as social businessmen, Florence Nightingale and landscape designer Frederick Law Olmsted. Throughout the Americas, Dees has recognized two thinking colleges focusing on business growth and entrepreneurship. The first focuses on organisation, income generation and economic planning as centres of high-impact companies, and the second focuses on innovative ideas. Many researchers have an integrated word that adapts to many different ways of creating change; others use the word to characterize those whose job generates large-scale transformative changes with unusual skill, bravery and tenacity. The word has proven helpful,

although there is no widely agreed definition because it builds on long-standing understandings of businessmen and uses them in fresh respects. It has launched fresh paths for conduct and techniques of assessment for individuals who are driven by a willingness to tackle such issues by showing how business characteristics can be channeled to tackle significant issues. There have always been social entrepreneurs. In either the outset moreover, they were called visionaries, social activists, philanthropists, revolutionaries or deities. Interest will indeed be assigned to their bravery, empathy and vision, but barely to their achievements' practical elements. Citizens can, therefore, be aware of St. Francis' moral doctrines but not how Franciscans were the fastest increasing order of their day in religion. Kids understand that Florence Nightingale served the injured, but did not build the first nursing college and revolutionize the development of the clinic. Gandhi is known for non-violent opposition protests, not for the construction of decentralisation, that allowed India to shift to self-regulation successfully. And all understand that on the steps of the Lincoln Memorial, Martin Luther King Jr. said, "I have a dream but few are aware that, as Philip Randolph and Bayard Rustin organized the March on Washington, they created sure that King's effect could last. In the development of many bodies and activities we take for granted, a cautious historian could recognize the concealed hand of social businessmen. But societies started to initiate wide organizational changes, allowing a big number of individuals to become businessmen, until about the seventeenth century. The change was started in Europe, where the monopolies of the Crown, the Church, feudalists and the guilds have limited trade, prevented the development and bound individuals to soil and churches for hundreds of years. There will be little room for autonomous trade, but there is little liberty or motivation to take advantage of their enterprise. As Robert Heilbronn describes in Worldly Philosopher's article, button manufacturers from France were detained in the seventeenth century for experimentation with fabric, and hundreds of investors had been sent to galleys, kept under the wheel, hanged and so on, solely since they carried colored calicos for marketing. In order to reject some economic and business influence, armies that reversed the ancient manner of life in Europe have forced the demographic development, urbanization, science progress, improvements in transport and acquired riches. At the end of the Enlightenment, the rights to 'life, freedom & ownership,' in the well-known formula of John Locke, furnished an ethical and theoretical structure for classical economics and freedom, especially the advent of liberalism and the principle of property rights. These concepts aided to

distinguish a fresh industry of culture from a personal industry where people could reorder manufacturing models to take advantage of their business

The company climate of the early 21st millennium has converted from easy and stable to complicated and vibrant environments that pose a severe danger to many companies. Ability to adapt and flexible have become the essential capacity, which is the capacity to adjust to evolving environments. The natural part of the market economy today is created by SMEs. It is unquestionable that they are important both for the domestic budget even from a microeconomic point of view. Currently, developments in tiny and medium-sized food company operations not only occur in the national world, they also become more and more internationally. The internationalization of the presented item is designed to implement present developments in a global company of Slovak Food SMEs and to generate fresh market opportunities natural development and market position enhancing. 2.1.8 Shift to Social Entrepreneurship for small and medium social Enterprises in Bangladesh.

WHY THE RESEARCH IS IMPORTANT WITH AN EMPIRICAL EVIDENCES

The majority-impact and academic-of Grameen Bank studies are done by economists and anthropologists, who are relying heavily on questionnaire investigations, generate quantitative data on the Bank's performance, and provide the webbed-eye perspective of the system. To my understanding, in this globally reputed credit scheme, no extensive scholarly research has been done. My thorough study presents a comparative analysis of the proven and helps us understand the system of the social entrepreneurship. This research is about social and economic structures so that the Bank can recognize how effective micro-loan creditors and recovery is, and how the micro-loans system impacts the borrower and community and the viability and development of the micro-lending sector. This analysis is about how micro-loan structure continues to be efficient for lenders and social stakeholders.

The findings from my economics on the Grameen bank will contribute to the global demand for new knowledge on micro-credit loans and growth of micro-enterprises. Throughout the last 25 years, researchers and campaigners have changed the emphasis from large infrared growth to small-scale participatory development.

The developmental transition was the result of the failure, by no means beneficial to the poor, of the modernisation paradigm (Rugers 1976) (Chambers 1986; Yunus 1995). The proponents of the

modernization model claim that poor people need tools to establish themselves and set up micro-enterprises that require minimal money and use their local know-how and skills.

The mixed method analysis of this thesis not only compliments the current research on the Bank of Grameen but also gives a different image from previous studies observations. My thesis raises issues about the traditional of Grameen Bank's small loans and about conservative views on women's progress and equality in society. In this article, the operational study of microcredit describes the lending framework for lenders and puts together the difference among quantitative and qualitative research. The study indicates growing violence and aggression towards lenders (which has not yet been reported) and provides several examples of increasing social tensions and conflict in reaction to lending and activities. The purpose of this study is to propose not only improvements in the practice and system of borrowing but also questions the orthodox view of the performance of micro credit and women's empowerment in society on the basis of theory.

A PROPOSAL FROM THE REVIEWAL JOURNEY: HOW MIGHT THE GOVERNMENT SUPPORT SOCIAL ENTERPRISE EFFECTIVELY

How might the government support social enterprise effectively? Although there is relative unimportance of a systematic and realistic approach to dealing with social entrepreneurs, there are five main methodologies for individual incidents involving municipal, county and city staff working with social entrepreneurs. With these approaches more systematically implemented, policymakers will help shift the dial to key social problems dramatically:

1. Promote social creativity-A company's growth phase is crucial for any entrepreneur. Government entrepreneurs will promote social creativity, helping to evaluate promising new solutions to social problem solving (Public innovator, 2008).
2. Building a favorable environment for social creativity and business—Creativity itself ensures that social enterprises move into new fields and often face unforeseen challenges along the way. The hurdles for social enterprises can be overcome by collective entrepreneurs. In fact, it can only enable social enterprises to reach critical mass by having legitimacy and drawing attention to a certain problem or projects (Public Innovator, 2008).
3. Recompense for exceptional performance in social entrepreneurship initiatives— Access to reliable sources of funding is vital for the productivity and viability of workable solutions. The

Government can help insure that effective approaches continue and increasing their effect by linking decisions on funding and success procurement to accomplish such solutions (Public innovator, 2008).

4. Scaling productive methods—it is often critical to broaden the scope of a tried and true alternative. But it is notoriously difficult for a positive program to gain legitimacy, approval for implementation or financing. Of extending the range of solutions that work by seeking out what works and allowing solutions to scale, government can play a crucial role (Public Innovationer, 2008).

5. Knowledge development—The government now acts as a critical database and guidelines for hedge fund managers. Clearer, more transparent criteria and easily accessible details (Public Innovator, 2008, J., Crawford, J. & Kelder, J.A. & Knox,2020), with some Sari constraints, A. I will play a critical part in obtaining information as said by Sari (2019).

MOVING FORWARD: HYPOTHESIS OF STUDY

Firstly, the accomplishment of social needs as a move towards the introduction of social enterprises in small and medium-sized businesses is a connection to business success and efficiency. The next theory, H1: The degree to which social needs are met as part of the developments in social entrepreneurship implementation has a stronger impact on the performance of industry, is therefore proposed to research the pattern of social entrepreneurship in developing economies, such as Bangladesh.

The second point is that imagination and innovation are shown to connect business success and results in SMEs as a pattern in social entrepreneurial execution. The following is hypothesis H2: H2: The degree of concentration on the creativity and innovation by small and medium-sized firms as part of developments in social entrepreneurship execution has a greater effect on business performance and growth, in order to investigate the elements of company models and structures used by social enterprises in developing economies such as Bangladesh.

The third theory is based on the idea that small and medium-sized businesses ' creative use of corporate capital as a phenomenon in social entrepreneurship is related to business success and performance. The following hypothesis H3 is formed to examine whether Bangladesh has scope and opportunities to expand entrepreneurship development: H3: a higher level of innovative use

of corporate resource by small and medium-sized social enterprises has a significant impact on corporate success.

The fourth hypothesis is based on a trend in social entrepreneurship that has a connection with corporate success and performance in environmental & sustainable development. In order to investigate the reasons and weaknesses of developing new systems and models in Bangladesh's small and medium-sized businesses, the concept is H4: the greater the emphasis of a small and medium-sized sector on environmental & sustainability problems, the greater the effect the organization has on the company's success and results.

The fifth hypothesis will explain that patterns in the application of social entrepreneurship have a correlation with progress and efficiency. A study of factors affecting the use and application of those mechanisms in the growth of SMEs in Bangladesh is one of the research objectives. The following theory is formulated to check a concept of causal interaction variables in conjunction with the research question about how these mechanisms are used and implemented: H5: The greater the combination of patterns for the adoption by private small and medium-sized enterprises in social enterprises becomes, the greater the effect on businesses' rates.

Conclusion

This paper seeks to propose a study of the role of social entrepreneurship in providing economic opportunities for the Bangladeshi people. On the basis of ongoing debates, ideas and hypotheses about the influence of public entrepreneurship in literature and society, it is discovered that customer entrepreneurship has expanded access to financial outlets, facilitated the use of social innovation to mitigate social issues, inspired communities and generated jobs. The very first three components generate an income for the underprivileged, thus facilitating employment opportunities, while the latter eliminate the deprivation of capacities that enable the underprivileged to participate and behave in the economy.

References

- Austin, J., Gutierrez, R., Ogliastris, E. and Reficco, R. (eds) (2006a). *Effective Management of Social Enterprises*. Cambridge, MA: David Rockefeller Center Series on Latin American Studies, Harvard University.
- Austin, J.E., Leonard, H., Reficco, E., & Wei-Skillern, J. (2004). *Corporate social entrepreneurship: A new vision of CSR*. Harvard Business School Working Paper No. 05-021. Boston: Harvard Business School.
- Brown, L. D., & Covey, J. G. (1987). Development organizations and organization development: Implications for a new paradigm. In W. Pasmore & R. Woodman (Eds.), *Research in organization change and development* (Vol. 1, pp. 59-88).
- Cernea, M. (1987). Farmer organizations and institution building for sustainable agricultural development. *Regional Development Dialogue*, 8(2), 1-24.
- Crawford, J., Kelder, J. A., & Knox, M. W. (2020). What Does It Take to Be a Social Entrepreneur?: Authentic Leaders and Their Effect on Innovation. In *Leadership Styles, Innovation, and Social Entrepreneurship in the Era of Digitalization* (pp. 282-310). IGI Global.
- Cuervo Ivaro, Domingo Ribeiro and Salvador Roig. (2007). *Entrepreneurship: Concepts, Theory and Perspectives*. Berlin: Springer Verlag and Heidelberg, 2007. 348 pp. ISBN 978-354048-542-2,
- Dees J. G. and Anderson B. B. (2003). *For-Profit Social Ventures*. In *Social entrepreneurship*, Eds. M. L. Kourilsky and W. B. Walstad. Birmingham, UK: Senate Hall Academic Publishing.
- Dees, J. G. (1998, January/February). Enterprising nonprofits: What do you do when traditional sources of funding fall short? *Harvard Business Review*, pp. 55-67.
- Dees, J.G. & Anderson, B.B. (2003). For-profit social ventures, *International Journal of Entrepreneurship Education* (special issue on social entrepreneurship), 2, 1-26.
- Dees, J.G. (1998). The meaning of "social entrepreneurship." Comments and suggestions contributed from the Social Entrepreneurship Founders Working Group. Durham, NC: Center for the Advancement of Social Entrepreneurship, Fuqua School of Business, Duke University. [Online] Available: <http://faculty.fuqua.duke.edu/centers/case/files/dees-SE.pdf>.
- EGEE 2004: Final Report of the Expert Group "Education for Entrepreneurship": Making Progress in promoting entrepreneurial attitudes and skills through Primary and Secondary education. Brussels February 2004. [Online] Available: http://europa.eu.int/comm/enterprise/entrepreneurship/support_measures/training_education/final_report_february.pdf.
- Emerson, J. & Twersky, F. (Eds.). (1996, September). *New social entrepreneurs: The success, challenge and lessons of non-profit enterprise creation*. San Francisco: Roberts Foundation, Homeless Economic Development Fund.
- Emerson, J. & Twersky, F. (Eds.). (1996, September). *New social entrepreneurs: The success, challenge and lessons of non-profit enterprise creation*. San Francisco: Roberts Foundation, Homeless Economic Development Fund.

- Greenwich, CT: JAI. Bryna, Mary Sanger, and Martin Levin. (1991). Using Old Stuff in New Ways: Innovation as a Case of Evolutionary Tinkering. *Journal of Policy Analysis and Management*, Vol. 10, No. 4, Fall.
- Haugh, Helen. (2005). A research agenda for social entrepreneurship. *Social Enterprise Journal*, Volume Number 1, Issue 1. March 2005, pp.1-13.
- Haugh, Helen. (2007). NEW STRATEGIES FOR A SUSTAINABLE SOCIETY: THE GROWING CONTRIBUTION OF SOCIAL Entrepreneurship, *Business Ethics Quarterly*, Volume 17, Issue 4. ISSN 1052-150X. pp. 743-749.
- Korten, D. C. (1980). Rural organization and rural development: A learning process approach. *Public Administration Review*, 40, 480-511.
- Krishna, A., Uphoff, N., & Esman, M. J. (Eds.). (1997). *Reasons for hope: Instructive experiences in rural development*. West Hartford, CT:
- Kumarian. Mair, J., Robinson, J. and Hockrts, K. (2006). *Social Entrepreneurship*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Martin, R. & Sally, O. (2007). Social Entrepreneurship the case for definition, spring 2007/ *STANFORD SOCIAL INNOVATION REVIEW* 29-39. [Online] Available: www.ssireview.org.
- Mosher-Williams, R. (ed.) (2006). 'Research on Social Entrepreneurship: Understanding and Contributing to an Emerging Field', *Occasional Papers Series No. 1.3, ARNOVA*.
- NCSEE 2004: Consortium for Entrepreneurship Education: National Content Standards for Entrepreneurship Education. [Online] Available: http://www.entre-ed.org/Standards_Toolkit/.
- Nicholls, A. (ed.) (2006b). *Social Entrepreneurship: New Models of Sustainable Social Change*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Nyssens, M. (ed.) (2006). *Social Enterprise*. London: Routledge.
- OECD. (1999). *Social Enterprises*. Paris: OECD
- Paul, S. (1982). *Managing development programs: The lessons of success*. Boulder, CO: West view.
- Perrini. (2006). *The New Social Entrepreneurship: What Awaits Elgar*, 2006. 341 pp. ISBN: 1 84542 781 5.
- Public Innovator. (2008). Connecting government with entrepreneurial solutions to today's toughest problems. [Online] Available: <http://www.publicinnovators.com/what-social-entrepreneurship>
- Reis, T. (1999). *unleashing the new resources and entrepreneurship for the common good: A scan, synthesis and scenario for action*. Battle Creek, MI: W.K. Kellogg Foundation
- Sari, A. I. (2019). Social Entrepreneurs and Innovation for the Unemployment. *International Journal of Economics and Management*, 1(3), 72-79.
- Wallace S. L. (1999). Social Entrepreneurship: The role of social purpose enterprises in facilitating community economic development, *Journal of Developmental Entrepreneurship*, 4, 2, pp.153-174.

Mr. Methun Molla is currently pursuing a ph.D. in the faculty of business and social entrepreneurship in research, the University of Kuala Lumpur (Unikl), Malaysia. I holds an MBA in business management studies from the University of Segi, Malaysia.my area of expertise in

research includes Marketing, Entrepreneurship, Organization Behavior, Strategy management, etc. I have several journal articles in the web of science and the Scopus indexed journal.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare. No funds were taken.

© 2020 by the authors. TWASP, NY, USA. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Assets of publishing with NAAR

- Global archiving of articles
- Immediate, free online access for all
- Rigorous peer review process
- Authors retain copyrights
- DOI for all articles

<https://twasp.info/journal/home>

The graphic features a central image of a green globe with a plant growing out of it, set against a background of radiating yellow and green lines.

Submit your article : editor@twasp.info